

HOW MUCH HAVE YOU PREPARED?

A STUDY ON RETIREMENT PLANNING AMONG MALAYSIAN CIVIL SERVANTS

RASHID ATING

Introduction

To quote Catherine Pulsifer, a Canadian writer and poet, “Retirement, a time to enjoy all the things you never had time to do when you worked.” Her words describe exactly what retirement should be as retirees would have much more free time compared to before they retired. As for finances, Malaysian civil service retirees receive pensions and gratuity from the government upon retirement. They receive a lump sum of money after spending 20, 30 or 40 years serving in the civil service. However, is that money sufficient for their retirement years, given the rising cost of living at present?

Main Issue

Retirement planning in the worldwide perspective works on the same principle. After completing the required years of service, retired civil servants reach the compulsory retirement age and will receive perks in the form of pension and gratuity. In Malaysia, retirees from the civil service receive a lump sum of money after retirement or from the private retirement scheme (PRS). This amount of money they receive after their retirement is for use to cover their daily expenses and prepare them for rainy days in the future. However, a news report in 2022 highlighted that most Malaysians, including civil servants, are not financially prepared for their retirement. This alarming finding shows that most Malaysians need to prepare for retirement planning. It also reveals that pension and gratuity alone are not enough to sustain civil servants’ and retirees’ lives post-retirement due to the high cost of living, inflation, market uncertainty and other factors.

Findings

In 2021, 1.6 million civil servants in Malaysia comprised 9.8 per cent of the total workforce (Povera, 2021). Even though the number seems insignificant, it still impacts government expenditure. Figure 1 shows that the Malaysian government’s pension costs have been steadily increasing from 2005 until 2019. On average, the government spends RM15.30 billion a year paying for retirees’ pensions with a minimum amount of RM1,100 being transferred to pensioners’

bank accounts on the 21st of each month. Looking at Figure 1, we can project that the amount will keep increasing to cater for the existing number of civil servants that will be retiring in the future.

*Note: Figures have been rounded up; 2018 and 2019 are revised and budget estimates. Source: Ministry of Finance’s Fiscal Outlook, (2019), past Economic Reports; Lim, (2018)

With the increasing cost of living, prudent spending is essential for the retiree to prepare for future emergencies. Using the life-cycle graph (Figure 3), the elderly or retirees are at stage 4 or the end stage of Retirement Planning, with estimated expenses of RM2000-3000 each month (Table 1). It is worth noting that the monthly living cost for seniors (whether singles or couples) are about the same as that for single (non-senior) public transport users and car owners. However, the significant difference between these two categories is seniors would have achieved what they wanted and want to have a stress-free time upon retirement. On the other hand,

Rashid Ating

Researcher, Institute of Advanced Studies (IAS)
Universiti Malaya, Kuala Lumpur

This work strictly represents the author’s personal view and is not made on behalf of any institutions or organizations. The author can be reached at rashid_ating@um.edu.my

the single non-retired person is generally a fresh graduate starting to build up their career. A 2021 study by the Social Wellbeing Research Centre (SWRC) proposed a minimum expenditure budget for retirees categorised as senior single and senior couple aged 60 years and above (working or not working) as in Figure 2. Since the compulsory retirement age in Malaysia is 60, retirees are considered to be in these categories.

Source: Social Wellbeing Research Centre (SWRC), 2021

Table 1 shows the estimated monthly cost expenses of a senior single and a senior couple for all major cities in Malaysia. After civil servants retire from the workforce, the senior single would need an average of RM2182 a month while senior couples would need at least RM2819 to have a decent life. Undoubtedly, more money is needed for expenses in urban areas such as the Klang Valley, Johor Bahru, Georgetown and Kota Kinabalu. In contrast, expenses are less in smaller towns like Alor Setar, Kuala Terengganu, and Kota Bahru. The highest estimated monthly costs for both senior singles and senior couples are in the Klang Valley (Central Region), and the least are in Alor Star (Northern Region). The table can guide a retiree as to where to move to after their retirement to reduce their expenses by looking at the estimated expenses needed in that city. A popular option for retirees is to move from a big to a small town after retirement to enjoy a peaceful and easy life.

Table 1: Estimated Total Cost for Household Category Per Month for Senior Singles and Senior Couples in All Cities in Malaysia

City/Region	Senior Single (RM)	Senior Couple (RM)
Klang Valley	RM2490	RM3170
Alor Setar	RM1990	RM2590
Kota Kinabalu	RM2250	RM2870
Johor Bahru	RM2310	RM2980
Kuala Terengganu	RM2060	RM2690
Kuching	RM2120	RM2740
Kuantan	RM2090	RM2720
Kota Bahru	RM2010	RM2630
Georgetown	RM2410	RM3080
Ipoh (prelim)	RM2110	RM2740
Seremban (prelim)	RM2210	RM2850
Melaka (prelim)	RM2140	RM2770

Source: Social Wellbeing Research Centre (SWRC), 2021

Conclusion

In conclusion, six steps can be used as a guide for retirees before they enter their retirement phase to ensure a smooth and happy retirement. First, identifying the income needed post-retirement. This can be achieved by implementing the replacement ratio method (pre-retirement lifestyle used to determine the post-retirement lifestyle) and the expenses model (detailing the expenses or commitment for the post-retirement period such as car and housing payment, food, clothes and other related costs). Both of these methods are quite different in application, but the main objective is to gauge the expenses of the retiree post-retirement. Secondly, determining the retirement capital, which can be split into

two methods, capital liquidation and capital preservation. These two methods differ from one another, intending to sustain the retirees after their retirement. Capital liquidation is more towards having the assets for the retiree's use to meet retirement need (for instance, the pension and PRS that they receive monthly), while capital preservation focuses on the retirement funds that must be able to generate an income for the retiree to sustain themselves after their retirement, such as investment in company shares and others. Step three is determining the current and future resources by channelling the income from retirement funds to something that can generate more revenue streams, such as investment-linked plans, unit trust, equity land and buildings instead of investing in unproductive lands and retirement homes. The fourth step is to calculate the retirement process status (RPS). The current assets are converted to future value by taking into account the interest rate in the future. The valuation of the assets might be too high or too low due to the inflation rate. Examples of the current assets that can be measured using the future value are shares, unit trusts, condominium, factory, life insurance in the form of endowments and others. Step five comprises calculating the retirement gap by subtracting the lump sum needed for retirement and the lump sum at retirement. Here, retirees can gauge if their saving is sufficient or not sufficient based on the gap. If there is a gap, their retirement funds need to be increased for their retirement and vice-versa. Lastly, retirees need to determine their funding needs during the pre-retirement period to meet the lump sum necessary during their retirement. Planning is crucial and needs to be executed early to maximize the output. As Benjamin Franklin said, "Failing to plan is preparing to fail".

Figure 3: Stages of Retirement Planning

